

Supplemental Table 1

B

Primers for Bag-1 KO				
Name	Target region	gRNA sequences	Primer sequences	Expected PCR product size
Guide A	Exon 2	TGAACCAGTTGTCCAAGACC	F: TTTCTTTTCTCCCCAGGCAAT R: TGTGGAACCCCTATGACCTC	118 bp
Guide B	Exon 3	GGTTGCCGGGTCATGTTAAT	F: GGAAACACCGTTGTCAGCAC R: ACAGGAGCAGGAGGGTATGA	252 bp
Guide C	Exon 6	AGGCTTGGTAAAAAAGGTTCC	F: ACAGGATACAGACCCAGGGA R: ACCACGCTCCTACACTACCT	337 bp
Primers for off-targets				
Name	Target region	Target gRNA	Primer sequences	
Off-target 1	RPL31P12 RNU6-1246P_chr1 – Chr1:73056651-73056673	gRNA A	F: TCGTCGGCAGCGTCACCTGGCAATATTCTCAGCCA R: GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGACATGAACTCTTCTGTGGCA	
Off-target 2	AC007682.1 AC097463.2_chr2 Chr 2: 52130030-52130052	gRNA C	F: TCGTCGGCAGCGTCCAGTCAGTCATCTCAGAGAAGACA R: GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGTGTGCTCTGCCAACTTTGTT	
Off-target 3	CTD-2183H9.7 F8_chrX chrX:154126403-154126425	gRNA B	F: TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAACACTGCAGCTGCGTATCT R: GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGAAGGCTGAAGAGTGCAC	

Supplemental Figure 1A

Bag-1 KO Guide A Forward

Sequence ID: Query_34093 Length: 84 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 4 to 80 Graphics ▼ Next Match ▲ F

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
99.0 bits(53)	1e-24	76/85(89%)	9/85(10%)	Plus/Plus

wt	TCATG-TTACCTCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAGACCTGGCCAGGTTG	2009
Bag-1 KO	TCATGATTA-CTCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAG-----CCAGGTTG	55

wt	TTGAAGAGGTCATAGGGTTCCACA	2034
Bag-1 KO	TTGAAGAGGTCATAGGGTTCCACA	80

targetting exon 2 (Guide A)

Target sequence
PAM

wt 5'-TACCTCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAGACCTGGCCAGGTTGTTGAAGAGGTCATAGGGG-3'

Bag-1 KO 5'-TAC--TCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAG-----CCAGGTTGTTGAAGAGGTCATAGGGG-3' (-7 bp)

Bag-1 KO Guide A Reverse

Sequence ID: Query_44885 Length: 66 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1 to 66 Graphics ▼ Next Match

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
99.0 bits(53)	1e-24	66/71(93%)	5/71(7%)	Plus/Plus

wt	1957	TACCTCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAGACCTGGCC
Bag-1 KO		TACCTCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAGACCTGGCC

wt	2017	GGTCATAGGGG	2027
Bag-1 KO	56	GGTCATAGGGG	66

targetting exon 2 (Guide A)

wt 5'-TACCTCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAGACCTGGCCAGGTTGTTGAAGAGGTCATAGGGG-3'

Bag-1 KO 5'-TACCTCCCAGCAGGGCAGCAGTGAACCAAGTGTCCAAGACCTGGCCAGGTTGTTGAAGAGGTCATAGGGG-3' (-6 bp)

Supplemental Figure 1B

Bag-1 KO Guide B Forward

Sequence ID: Query_36079 Length: 64 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1 to 64 [Graphics](#) ▼ Next Match ▲

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
91.6 bits(49)	2e-22	64/70(91%)	6/70(8%)	Plus/Plus

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wt      3644 ATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTTAATGGGAAAAAGGTAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCT 3703
          |||
Bag-1 KO  ATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTT---GGG--AAAGGTAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCT 54
          |||
wt      3704 CAGAATCAAA 3713
          |||
Bag-1 KO  55 CAGAATCAAA 64
    
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targetting exon 3 (Guide B)

Target sequence PAM

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wt      5'-ATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTTAATTGGGAAAAAGGTAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCTCAGAATCAAA-3'
Bag-1 KO 5'-ATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTT-----GGGAAA---GGTAAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCTCAGAATCAAA-3' (-6 bp)
    
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Bag-1 KO Guide B Reverse

Sequence ID: Query_16017 Length: 215 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 12 to 212 [Graphics](#) ▼ Next Match ▲

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
348 bits(188)	4e-99	201/206(98%)	5/206(2%)	Plus/Minus

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wt      3612 GGAAACACCGTTGTCAGCACTTGGAAATACAAGATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTTAATGGGAA 3671
          |||
Bag-1 KO  212 GGAAACACCG-TGTCAGCACTTGGAAATACAAGATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTT---GGGAA 158
          |||
wt      3672 AAAGGTAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCTCAGAATCAAATGACTGAAGTCTTTTATA 3731
          |||
Bag-1 KO  7 AAAGGTAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCTCAGAATCAAATGACTGAAGTCTTTTATA 98
    
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targetting exon 3 (Guide B)

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wt      5'-ATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTTAATTGGGAAAAAGGTAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCTCAGAATCAAA-3'
Bag-1 KO 5'-ATGGTTGCCGGGTCATGTT-----GGGAAA---GGTAAATGCTTTTTCCATCAGAAATCCTCAGAATCAAA-3' (-5 bp)
    
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Supplemental Figure 1C

Bag-1 KO Guide C Forward

Sequence ID: Query_28709 Length: 296 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 12 to 292 [Graphics](#)

[▼ Next Match ▲](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
449 bits(243)	1e-129	281/296(95%)	15/296(5%)	Plus/Plus
wt	TCACATTTACATTGGTGACCTGTGACCTGTTTTGTGACTGTGGGTGTTTCTTATGTGCT	8755		
Bag-1 KO	TCACATTTACATTGGTGACCTGTGACCTGTTTTGTGACTGTGGGTGTTTCTTATGTGCT	71		
wt	CTCATGTCATTTTCACTGAGGATTATTTGTTACATGTTTACTATTTACTAACTTGATTA	8815		
Bag-1 KO	CTCATGTCATTTTCACTGAGGATTATTTGTTACATGTTTACTATTTACTAACTTGATTA	131		
wt	TCAACTTACTCTTCCATAGATCCTGCCAGAAAATTTCAAAGACAGTAGATTGAAAAGGAA	8875		
Bag-1 KO	TCAACTTACTCTTCCATAGATCCTGCCAGAAAATTTCAAAGACAGTAGATTGAAAAGGAA	191		
wt	AGGCTTGGTAAAAAAGTTGAGGTGAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTGTAATATGT	8935		
Bag-1 KO	AGGCTT-----GGTGAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTGTAATATGT	236		
wt	TAATGTGTAGGTATGTGTTTTATCTGTTCAAAATCAGGTAGTGTAGGAGCGTGGT	8991		
Bag-1 KO	TAATGTGTAGGTATGTGTTTTATCTGTTCAAAATCAGGTAGTGTAGGAGCGTGGT	292		

targetting exon 6 (Guide C)

wt 5'-TAGATTGAAAAGGAAAGGCTTGGTAAAAAAGGTTTCAGGTGAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTGTAA-3'
 Bag-1 KO 5'-TAGATTGAAAAGGAAAGGCTT-----GGTGAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTGTAA-3'(-15bp)

Supplemental Figure 1C

Bag-1 KO Guide C Reverse

Sequence ID: Query_12755 Length: 291 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 9 to 289 [Graphics](#) ▼ Next Match ▲

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
446 bits(241)	2e-128	281/297(95%)	16/297(5%)	Plus/Minus
wt	TACAGGATACAGACCCAGGGAAAGGGTTCTGAAAATGGATATCACATTTACATTGGTGA	8713		
Bag-1 KO	TACAGGATACA-ACCCAGGGAAAGGGTTCTGAAAATGGATATCACATTTACATTGGTGA	231		
wt	CCTGTGACCTGTTTTGTGTACTGTGGGTGTTTCTTATGTGCTCTCATGTCAATTTCACTG	8773		
Bag-1 KO	CCTGTGACCTGTTTTGTGTACTGTGGGTGTTTCTTATGTGCTCTCATGTCAATTTCACTG	171		
wt	AGGATTATTTGTTACATGTTTACTATTTACTAACTTGTATTATCAACTTACTCTCCATA	8833		
Bag-1 KO	AGGATTATTTGTTACATGTTTACTATTTACTAACTTGTATTATCAACTTACTCTCCATA	111		
wt	GATCCTGCCAGAAAAATTTCAAAGACAGTAGATTGAAAAGGAAAGGCTTGGTAAAAAAGGT	8893		
Bag-1 KO	GATCCTGCCAGAAAAATTTCAAAGACAGTAGATTGAAAAGGAAAGGCTTGGT-----	60		
wt	TCAGGTGAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTGTAATATGTTAATGTGTAGGTATG	8950		
Bag-1 KO	-----GAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTGTAATATGTTAATGTGTAGGTATG	9		

targetting exon 6 (Guide C)

wt 5'-CAGTAGATTGAAAAGGAAAGGCTTGGTGAAGTTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTG-3'
 Bag-1 KO 5'-CAGTAGATTGAAAAGGAAAGGCTTGGT-----GAGTTGTGTAATAGTGCACGACAAGGTG-3'(-15bp)

Supplemental Figure 2

Supplemental Figure 3

A

MCF-7

B

A

MDA-MB-231

B

Supplemental Figure 6

Supplemental Figure 7

